

USE OF VANADOUS SULPHATE AS A REDUCING AGENT. PART III. ESTIMATION OF CERIUM.

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Cerium has been estimated volumetrically in the presence of other rare earths (e.g., in monazite sand) by reducing it with vanadous sulphate. Cerous salt is first oxidised to the ceric state with ammonium persulphate in presence of a measured amount of sulphuric acid. After removing the excess of persulphate the ceric solution is titrated with vanadous sulphate using diphenylamine as an internal indicator.

Cerium and its compounds are at present very important commercial products and a number of methods (Knorre, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1897, 11, 685, 717; Power and Shedden, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1900, 19, 636; Brauner, *Chem. News*, 1895, 71, 285; Willard and Young, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 1379) has been proposed for its accurate determination. In the gravimetric procedures, the separation of cerium from the other rare earths when occurring together is absolutely essential—a process which is very tedious and at the same time consumes too much time. Volumetric procedures are, however, much simpler. It depends either upon the oxidation of Ce^{++} to Ce^{+++} or reduction of Ce^{+++} to Ce^{++} . It is much more rapid and no separation is necessary from the other rare earths. Among the volumetric processes Knorre's classical method of reducing the ceric salt with an excess of hydrogen peroxide and titrating the excess with potassium permanganate is mostly employed for the estimation of cerium. Cerous salt is first oxidised to the ceric state by an alkali persulphate. The exact conditions for carrying out the oxidation have been carefully studied by Knorre (*loc. cit.*) and also by Lindeman and Hafsted. (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1927, 70, 43).

In a previous communication (Banerjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 198), it has been stated that ceric salts in acid solution are reduced by vanadous sulphate.

A method based on this reaction has been developed for the quantitative estimation of cerium. The ceric salt is reduced with an excess of vanadous sulphate which is then titrated back with a standard potassium permanganate solution; or the ceric sulphate is directly titrated with the vanadous sulphate solution using diphenylamine as an internal indicator. The end-point is quite sharp and is indicated by the disappearance of the beautiful bluish purple colour which is produced by the interaction of ceric ion with diphenylamine. Experiments were carried

out using both the methods and the results were found to be satisfactory. In the presence of iron, selective reduction takes place and it is only when the blue colour has completely disappeared that the iron begins to be reduced. When the ceric salt is reduced with an excess of vanadous sulphate as stated above, the iron is no doubt reduced to the ferrous state, but it is completely reoxidised at the time of back titration with potassium permanganate.

The cerium solution must be absolutely free from nitric acid or nitrates or any other substances which may oxidise the vanadous sulphate solution.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Analysis of Pure Cerous Oxalate.

Pure cerous oxalate, $Ce_2(C_2O_4)_3, 10H_2O$ (4.7766 g.) free from other rare earths was heated in a porcelain basin with concentrated sulphuric acid until white fumes of sulphur trioxide were evolved. After cooling, the mass was diluted with water and the solution made up to one litre. A known volume of this solution was oxidised by ammonium persulphate, strictly following the conditions as laid down by Knorre (*loc. cit.*) and Lindemann and Hafsted (*loc. cit.*), cooled to the room temperature and diluted to about 200 c.c. with air-free distilled water. 5-10 C.c. of concentrated sulphuric acid and two drops of an 1% solution of diphenylamine in sulphuric acid were added and the solutions titrated with the vanadous sulphate in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide until the blue colour had completely disappeared. The strength of the vanadous sulphate solution was determined with a standard ceric sulphate solution.

TABLE I.

Strength of vanadous sulphate soln. = $1.092 N/10$, 1 c.c. = 0.01531 g. of Ce.

No.	Amount of Ce-oxalate taken.	Vol. of vanadous soln. reqd.	% of Ce found.	% of Ce in $Ce_2(C_2O_4)_3, 10 H_2O$.
I.	100 c.c. (0.4776 g.)	12 c.c.	38.48%	
II.	100 (")	11.95	38.32	
III.	125 (0.5970)	15.0	38.47	38.71%
IV.	150 (0.7164)	18.05	38.59	

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In the second series of estimations ceric salt was reduced with an excess of vanadous sulphate solution and the excess was titrated back with 0·1N-potassium permanganate solution. Vanadous sulphate was in this case standardised with permanganate.

TABLE II.

Strength of VSO₄ soln. = 1·78 N/10.

No.	Amount of Ce-oxalate taken.	Vol. of vanadous soln. added.	Vol. of KMnO ₄ soln. added.	% of Ce found.	% of Ce in Ce ₂ (C ₂ O ₄) ₃ ·10H ₂ O.
I.	50 c.c. (0·2388 g.)	10 c.c.	11·25 c.c.	38·45%	
II.	75 (0·3582)	15	16·9	38·37	
III.	100 (0·4776)	20·0	22·55	38·31	38·71%
IV.	(..)	20·1	22·7	38·39	

Analysis of a Commercial Sample of Ceric Sulphate.

A solution of about 0·1N strength was prepared by dissolving the ceric sulphate in water containing sufficient sulphuric acid so as to prevent hydrolysis. A known volume of this solution was titrated in the usual way with vanadous sulphate and the results were compared with the values obtained by Knorre's method (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE III.

Strength of vanadous sulphate soln. = 1·227N/10.

1 c.c. = 0·01721 g. of Ce.

No.	Vol. of ceric sulphate soln.	Vol. of vanadous soln. reqd.	Amount of Ce found by present method.	Knorre's method.
I.	10 c.c.	7·20	0·01239 g./c.c.	
II.	20	14·45	0·01243	
III.	25	18·05	0·01242	0·01248 g./c.c.
IV.	25	18·0	0·01239	

Estimation of Cerium in Monazite Sand.

The sand (11.3562 g.) was digested with concentrated sulphuric acid and after filtering and washing the insoluble residue the solution was made up to 1 litre. From a known volume of this solution, the rare earths after precipitation as oxalate were dissolved in sulphuric acid and the cerium was estimated in the same way as described in the analysis of pure cerous oxalate.

TABLE IV.

Strength of vanadous soln. = 1.092N/10.

1 c.c. = 0.01531 g. of Ce.

No.	Wt. of monazite sand taken.	Vol. of vanadous soln. used.	Percentage Ce found by Author.	Percentage Ce found by Knorre's method.
I.	0.4542 g. (40 c.c.)	7.0 c.c.	23.59%	
II.	0.5678 (50)	8.70	23.47	23.6%
III.	0.9084 (80)	14.1	23.76	

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